

The role of GIS in smart farming and sustainable agriculture

Apoorva Sharma^{1*}, H. K. Sharma¹, Konga Upendar² and Arun Kumar¹

¹G. B. Pant University of Agriculture & Technology, Pantnagar, Uttarakhand, India

²Infyz Solutions, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

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Abstract

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) play a vital role in smart farming and sustainable agriculture by integrating spatial data with advanced analytics for precise decision-making. GIS enhances precision agriculture, soil and water management, crop monitoring, climate resilience, and sustainable land use planning. By leveraging satellite imagery, GPS, and remote sensing, GIS enables real-time monitoring, optimized resource allocation, and early detection of pests and diseases. Despite challenges like high costs and technical expertise requirements, future advancements in AI, IoT, and big data analytics will further enhance GIS applications, making agriculture more efficient, sustainable, and climate-resilient.

***Corresponding author:** Apoorva Sharma., G. B. Pant University of Agriculture & Technology, Pantnagar, Uttarakhand, India
India; Email: 59296@gbpuat.ac.in

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